

DEVELOPMENT OF THE COMPETENCE OF INFORMATION RECEIVING OF FUTURE TECHNOLOGICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS AS A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM

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Abstract. *In this article, the theoretical problem of personality formation is presented as a pedagogical problem that fully meets the requirements of the reforms implemented in society today. It is resistant to competition in the production sector that is able to adapt to sudden changes, and also works effectively at the level of the requirements for the qualifications of specialists are covered in the labor market.*

Keywords: *information, technological, labor education, competence.*

Introduction

One of the main goals of teaching technological education in general secondary schools is to introduce students to the types of mental and physical work, processes and professions, to form their initial work skills and qualifications, interest in work and hard work, to teach them to appreciate work and professions, to understand their importance, and to prepare them for choosing a profession. It consists in carrying out their pre-professional training and forming a personal quality and mindset that allows them to participate in labor activities for the welfare of society and individuals.

Technological education is a process of mental and physical activities performed by students under the guidance of a teacher and as a result, they acquire knowledge about work tools and processes, as well as practical knowledge and skills that necessary to perform production work in a certain field, consciously choose a profession, and society and is to develop personal qualities and thoughts that allow them to participate in labor activities for the well-being of the individual.

RESULT

The lessons that are organized in the school on technology education include the teaching of basic information related to the content of various production areas, the ability to use measurement and inspection tools, information sources, to perform labor practices, and to draw conclusions by comparing the achieved work results with the established requirements.

To provide knowledge about the techniques and technologies used in various fields of the national economy, to create an opportunity to get acquainted with various fields of human activity through practical work, to teach students the means of producing high-quality, competitive consumer goods, labor products and delivering the produced products to consumers based on the requirements of the laws of the market economy. work is to form and develop management (managerial) elements, patronage, business qualities.

To restore and develop the national spirit, way of life, and traditions of the people by inculcating the desire for knowledge and love of work, respect for working people, educating them in the spirit of community and loyalty to the Motherland, and teaching folk crafts. It is intended to teach national values, historical monuments, the rich heritage of folk masters, and to strengthen the skills of using them in practical activities. It consists of the use of tools, equipment, devices

used in various types of professional activities, the formation of general labor knowledge and skills in students, the formation of general labor culture, the qualities that are the basis for choosing professions according to their interests, abilities, and professional inclinations.

It is assumed that students from 5th to 9th grade of technological education should prepare for at least three fields of study. For example, girls, boys and general directions for them can be selected. In this regard, tasks such as recruiting students to choose a profession are solved in most educational subjects, together with technological education. In solving these tasks, technological education is of particular importance, because it is convenient to engage students in productive work, to introduce them to the basics of modern production, to instill in them a love for modern labor professions, and to form a sufficiently complete image of the same. conditions arise.

In addition to the specified tasks, secondary tasks are also set, and they are mainly solved within the framework of technological education, or they are tasks of a general secondary school and are carried out with the help of specific special tools. For example, the development of technical creativity, participation in experimental work occurs mainly in the process of technological education in school conditions and extracurricular activities organized on its basis. The same can be said about the formation of practical knowledge and skills related to material handling, machine maintenance, etc. In the process of technological training, physical activity is combined with mental activity. Pupils will have to solve a number of creative tasks such as design of objects, development of technology for their preparation. Thus, technological education is carried out together with thinking activities, which allows the intellectual development of students.

In the process of technological education, conditions are created for aesthetic education. If students make beautiful things, they will get moral satisfaction and aesthetic pleasure from benefiting the society. In this way, artistic taste is also cultivated in them, correct ideas about the appropriateness of forms are formed. The requirements for the content of technological education as an educational subject arise from the second-level tasks:

1. It is appropriate to divide the content of technological education into stages taking into account the age characteristics of students and the tasks set in the educational process.
2. The content of educational programs should provide consistency between the stages of education. For this, it is necessary to create programs for all classes according to a single structure. descriptions of the main occupations related to the processing of these materials.
3. Provide different options to ensure differentiation of technological education content. It is necessary to determine at what stages of technological education it is appropriate to classify its content and what should be followed in its implementation.
4. Students can be trained in different programs, but they must have the same level of understanding of the basics of modern production, and for this, it is necessary to include some stable amount of knowledge and skills in all programs. This, in turn, makes it possible to ensure that the polytechnic training of students is at the same level.

Today, in solving the scientific, theoretical and practical, material-technical, social-pedagogical problems of technological education, in reforming its traditional content, the following imbalances and contradictions are evident:

- that scientific and technical skills, advanced production technologies, new forms and content of modern economy and economic management are not sufficiently reflected in the means and methods of technological education;

- the current traditional content, purpose, form, means and methods of technological education do not reflect the national ethnic, territorial historical characteristics of our Republic and criteria of oriental thinking; insufficient development of the pedagogical, psychological, physiological and didactic foundations of the mechanisms of its implementation, taking into account the unique features of technological education;

- disproportion of the levels of professional qualifications of pedagogues being trained in higher pedagogical educational institutions with promising aspects of technological education that have not been implemented in general secondary schools.

Result and discussion

The shortcomings and contradictions mentioned above are the main reasons for the need for radical renewal and reform of technological education. The conducted observations showed that students' attention to technological education in the system of general secondary schools of our republic is not enough. The main reason for this is that the existing programs for preparing students for work cannot satisfy the demands and interests of the young generation, which is growing in the current socio-economic conditions. Therefore, a technological education teacher is a person who provides information on new techniques and technologies to students of general secondary schools. He should be a person who is knowledgeable in all aspects, talented in relation to his profession. For this, he should acquire deep knowledge of general professional subjects in higher pedagogical educational institutions, and be able to retain them in his work.

In order to achieve this goal, it is necessary to perform the following educational and developmental tasks: The implementation of the National Personnel Training Program aims at training competent personnel with a bold, independent, creative thinking, competent, knowledgeable specialist who can ensure the modern development of Uzbekistan in accordance with international requirements. In the introduction of the updated educational system, it is an important requirement of today that every young teacher should have the ability to form the professional competence related to the subject and the education of the mature generation, and to be able to maintain them consistently in the pedagogical activity.

The teacher's professional competence is characterized by the process of adopting pedagogical solutions. This increases the relevance of the problem of development of pedagogues, in particular, to be able to see the problems that arise in the educational process, to independently set specific pedagogical goals and problems, to find their solutions, to analyze, to evaluate the obtained results. First, let's talk about the concepts of competence and competence. The competence tariff is similar and replaces (complements) each other. Also, the tariff of pedagogical competence is as follows. 1.1 concepts of competence are common.

Competence is a requirement for the educational training of a specialist necessary for quality productive activity in a certain field.

Competence is the acquisition of competences related to the subject of activity by a person.

Competence is expressed by the student's acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for the implementation of personal and socially significant professional activities and their ability to retain them in professional activities. Here, the essence of the concept of "competence" is revealed, which is manifested in the following two aspects: competence as a set of personal qualities of students and basic requirements of the professional field.

Picture 1. Competence

Due to the fact that the educational content is grouped in the curriculum blocks of subjects (for all subjects), interdisciplinary (for a set of subjects) and subjects (for a specific subject), it is possible to recognize the following three levels of competence;

1. Basic competence (according to humanitarian, socio-economic content of education);
2. Interdisciplinary competence (according to the specific scope of educational subjects and educational blocks of general professional training);
3. Competence in one subject (subject) (according to having a clear and known opportunity within a special educational subject).

Basic competence is determined at the level of educational blocks and academic subjects for each stage of education in pedagogical higher education institutions. In determining the order of basic competence, the essence of social and personal experience, in accordance with the main goals of professional pedagogical education, becomes vital in the process of organizing professional activity in social society. From this point of view, the basic competence is divided into the following types: comprehensive, social and cultural, academic knowledge, information acquisition, communicative, social activity, improvement of the personality of the individual.

Conclusion

In this article, the teacher's competence to receive information is considered a necessary link in the basic competencies and his professional activity. It is known that independent search, analysis, selection, processing of information by means of real objects (television, television, tape recorder, telephone, fax, computer, printer, modem) and information technologies (audio and video recording, e-mail, mass media, Internet), skills such as storage and transmission are formed. This competence ensures the skills of the young teacher in relation to educational subjects and the field of education, as well as information in the surrounding world. At the same time, the range of professional competences of the teacher is quite wide. The pedagogue's competence to receive information is to reflect the existence of a complex of knowledge, expertise, skills and reflexive instructions in interaction with the information environment. Information acquisition competence is a professionally important integrative quality of a person, characterized by the degree of reduction of the set of competencies necessary for obtaining and functioning in the information world.

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